

CoolResearch Institute

CoolResearch is an international research institute. The researchers working in the institute conduct experiments, analyze their results, write reports and publish their data and reports to share with the research community.

Jane is a researcher who studies biology, focusing on brain structure. She has separate tools to collect, document, and analyze the data. She also builds tables and charts to visualize the data and put it online to share her results with others. She likes to automate this process and prevent context switching to stay focused by working with a single tool that assists her complete her research tasks. Other researchers in her team will use this tool as well. She currently generates simple tables and charts, and she wants to have more aesthetically pleasing visualization for her reports.

Her main concerns are;

- Having a single tool to streamline her research tasks: The software tool should be able to integrate seamlessly with the tools that Jane currently uses to collect, document, and analyze her data. This would allow her to work with a single tool that assists her in completing her research tasks.
- Automatically create the content for her research in the form of tables and charts: The software tool should be able to automatically create tables and charts based on the data that Jane inputs into the tool. This would save her time and prevent the need for manual data visualization.
- Create different types of charts to visualize her data: The software tool should offer a variety of chart types that she can use to represent her data. This could include bar charts, line charts, scatter plots, and more.
- Publish her reports and data online: The software tool should allow Jane to publish her reports and data online, making them accessible to other researchers in her field. This could involve integration with a platform such as GitHub or a specialized research repository.